

APPLICATION OF CLOUD TECHNOLOGIES IN EDUCATION

Isgender Tagangylyjov^{1*}, Oguljan Gawirova²

^{1,2}Oguz Han Engineering and Technology University of Turkmenistan, Ashgabat, Turkmenistan.

*Corresponding author

Today, the Internet is available everywhere. This has a great impact on the uninterrupted use of the Internet in the educational process as well. Therefore, it is more important to study the use of the Internet in the educational process in this field [1].

First, cloud computing is becoming more popular these days due to its ease of use. Students, teachers, and students can access content from any phone, computer, or iPad. This internet accessibility not only allows students, learners and teachers to be able to access the system from anywhere, but also extends the learning of students or students beyond the confines of the traditional four walls of the classroom. "With today's technology, student learning is no longer in the classroom. "The learning environment can be improved so that students can access learning resources anywhere, anytime," he said. Easy access to classroom content allows students to learn at their own pace, helping them think critically about information and gain deeper understanding. they can conduct and design lessons that allow the student to engage in extracurricular activities of the student's interest.

Second, cloud computing can improve collaboration among students as well as between students and teachers. "Google Docs and the entire G Suite system for English classrooms are changing the way we interact with each other. "This collaboration helps kids make real connections with text and information." Using apps like Google Docs and Google Slides can help students get real-time feedback from teachers on their work. As Barkley points out, " Collaborative learning is a pedagogy that emphasizes that when students and teachers work together to create knowledge, people create meaning together and the process is enriched and developed.

Third, using applications such as Google Classroom, cloud computing can help students and teachers organize and facilitate classroom communication. Google Classroom is an online learning management system that can host all of your classroom content. An online education system reduces the paperwork that teachers are used to. Teachers no longer have to carry paper assignments home because they can access information from any device. Also, students don't have to worry about not being on form or on assignments. Google Classroom is versatile, easy to use from both staff and student perspectives, and allows for easy collaboration . Using Google Classroom makes teachers and students better organized because it allows students and teachers to organize course content in Google Classroom. It also allows students and teachers to communicate with each other in an easy way [2].

Availability of data in the cloud is another advantage. Because students and faculty can instantly store and retrieve materials on remote servers, they can work from anywhere with an Internet connection and collaborate with classmates and peers without being in the same room.

Cloud technologies provide a secure Internet connection, which allows teachers to adopt online platforms for assigning and tracking homework assignments. By using all resources in the cloud, teachers can also focus on virtual learning. This flexibility has made cloud computing a major advancement in education, allowing all schools and colleges to better serve their students.

Cloud computing makes education more efficient and accessible. As education technology continues to change, many businesses struggle to ease the transition. Therefore, accelerating the adoption of cloud technologies in the education sector is an important issue.

REFERENCES

- [1]. <https://www.computer.org/publications/tech-news/build-your-career/cloud-technologies-in-the-education-system/>
- [2]. <https://pressbooks.pub/techandcurr2019/chapter/cloudcomputing/>